

Mn^{II} catalyzed oxidation of hexane-1,6-diamine by diperiodatocuprate(III) in aqueous alkaline medium – A kinetic and mechanistic approach

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Abstract : The kinetics of Mn^{II} catalyzed oxidation of hexane-1,6-diamine (HDA) by diperiodatocuprate(III) (DPC) in aqueous alkaline medium was monitored spectrophotometrically ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 415 \text{ nm}$) at constant ionic strength of 0.1 mol dm^{-3} and 301 K. The reaction shows 1 : 4 stoichiometry between HDA and DPC. The reaction is of first order in [DPC] and [Mn^{II}] and less than unit order in [HDA] and [alkali], periodate has retarding effect on reaction rate. The ionic strength and dielectric constant of the medium has no significant effect on the rate of the reaction. The added Cu^{II} product also has no effect on the rate of reaction. The main product caprolactam was identified by FTIR, GCMS, NMR, DSC and TGA. The active forms oxidant was detected [Cu(H₂IO₆)(H₂O)₂]. The rate law and reaction mechanism involving three different complexes was proposed. The equilibrium constants and rate constant were calculated. The activation parameters were deliberated for catalyzed and uncatalyzed reactions at different temperatures.

Keywords : Hexane-1,6-diamine, monoperiodatocuprate(III), MnO₂, oxidation, kinetics, mechanism.

Introduction

Chemical kinetics provides hands on information about reaction mechanism and factors affecting the rate. This kinetic study is very much essential for the chemical and pharmaceutical industries. Kinetics of various chemical reactions can be studied by titrimetric, stopped flow technique, flash photolysis, spectrophotometric and cyclic voltametric methods. Presently, in this paper we are reporting kinetics of Mn^{II} catalyzed oxidation of hexane-1,6-diamine by diperiodatocuprate(III) in aqueous alkaline medium by spectrophotometric method. The selected reductant HDA is the colorless water soluble compound with a strong amine odor. In earlier days it was produced by the hydrogenation of adiponitrile. HDA is moderately toxic, stable in air but combustible, due to its

bifunctional structure it is used almost exclusively for the production of polyamides. Hexamethylene diisocyanate generated from hexane-1,6-diamine used as a monomer feedstock in the production of polyurethane. It also serves as a cross-linking agent in epoxy resins. HDA is a good chelating agent which is capable of binding to transition metal ions in the higher oxidation state to form chelate. The substance DPC is a flexible oxidant¹, stable in aqueous medium and has multiple equilibria between different Cu^{III} species. Cu^{III} has been investigated as a reactive intermediate in some biological reactions², electron transfer reactions³ and as an analytical reagent⁴. Mn^{II} is used as an efficient catalyst in many redox reactions⁵. The literature survey reveals that the considerable amount of work has been done on the oxidation of

amines⁶ but only a few studies were found on the kinetics of oxidation of aliphatic diamines⁷. There are no reports on the title reaction; therefore, the reaction was investigated in detail to know the different active species and to arrive at realistic mechanism.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry :

Different sets of reaction mixtures containing various ratios of HDA to DPC in the presence of constant amounts of OH⁻ and KNO₃ were kept overnight in closed flasks. The unreacted [DPC] was estimated by spectrophotometrically. The results indicated 1 : 4 stoichiometry as given in the following equation,

Product analysis :

The reaction mixture of HDA with excess amount of DPC was refluxed for two hours to ensure the completion of reaction. During the refluxing process the yellow colored reaction mixture was turned to dark green color then after gradually turns to blue color. The refluxed mixture was cooled; the semi solid copper-nylon 6 complex separates out in the form of fluffy soft material. The complex was filtered using Whatman paper and was thoroughly washed with warm distilled water till it turns to lawn color. The complex was characterized by FTIR spectrum and compared with normal nylon 6 (Table 2). The band at 1032.27 cm⁻¹ was assigned to the C-N stretching of aliphatic amine which was not intense and shifted to 13 cm⁻¹ lower frequency and the combined absorbance of the N-H and C-N amide stretch at 1509.41 cm⁻¹ was also shifted 42 cm⁻¹ to lower frequency. Moreover, the spectrum shows the strong carbonyl group absorption band at 1618.04 cm⁻¹ was shifted 27 cm⁻¹ to lower frequency than normal nylon 6. These shifts clearly specify the formation of said complex shown in Table 2. Formation of this complex was observed when reaction mixture refluxed between

220–240 °C, otherwise reaction ends in caprolactum which is stable till 45 °C.

The filtrate was condensed by warming on a hot plate and cooled as a result water soluble colorless crystalline n-(6-aminohexyl)hydroxylamine (C₆H₁₆ON₂) intermediate compound separates. This intermediate compound n-(6-aminohexyl)hydroxylamine was also characterized by FTIR spectrum, ¹H NMR spectrum and GC-MS mass spectrum. The FTIR spectrum of n-(6-aminohexyl)hydroxylamine indicates clearly for hydroxyl group (at 3400.01 cm⁻¹) and not for carbonyl group. This confirms the partial oxidation of amino group. The degree of unsaturation (DoU) for intermediate compound n-(6-aminohexyl)hydroxylamine (C₆H₁₆ON₂) is zero. The ¹H NMR (D₂O, 400 MHz) spectrum (Fig. 1) shows chemical shifts at 1.656, 1.674, 1.689, 2.247 and 2.088 ppm and corresponds to the protons named as i, a and b of the group -NH₂, HO-HN. The chemical shifts at 2.994, 3.005, 3.011, 3.022, 3.028 and 3.038 ppm refers to the protons named as c and h of CH₂ group that is linked to -NH and NH₂. The chemical shifts at 1.340, 1.384, 1.392, 1.440, 1.450, 1.466 and 1.483 ppm assigned to the protons named as d, e, f, g of CH₂ group linked to the alkyl chain of (C₆H₁₆ON₂). The GC-MS spectrum of n-(6-aminohexyl)hydroxylamine which showed molecular volume of 133 cubic Angstrom unit. Thus isolated intermediate compound reacts further with DPC in aqueous alkaline medium and forms colorless solid compound caprolactam which was confirmed by FTIR, NMR, GC-MS, DSC and TGA. The side product ammonia was confirmed by Nessler's reagent. Caprolactam was identified (m.p. 69.2–69.5 °C) by FTIR (KBr; cm⁻¹); spectrum showed the strength of C(O)NH bands around 3500–2654, 1630–1690, (C=O, 1655.21), 1562.71 and (C-N) 1080–1360, (C-H) 2800–3000, 1350–1450; ¹H NMR measurements were carried out on instrument : Bruker, Model, Av 400 proton frequency 400 MHz NMR spectrometer, SAIF, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore. The chemical shifts were measured and D₂O solvent used. ¹H NMR (D₂O, 400 MHz) spectrum showed chemical shifts; 8.429 (1H, N-H protons, m),

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Fig. 1. ¹H NMR spectrum of n-(6-aminohexyl)hydroxylamine, the intermediate product of hexane-1,6-diamine by diperiodatocuprate(III) in aqueous alkaline medium.

3.197 (3H, CH₂ protons, m), 3.176, 3.86, 3.908, 2.372 (CH₂CO protons, m), 2.161, 2.140 and 1.886 to 1.486 (CH₂-CH₂-CH₂, m); GC-MS spectrum (Fig. 2) showed molecular volume of 113 cubic Angstrom unit. The thermal properties of caprolactam were monitored using Differential Scanning Calorimetry, DSC (Instrument DSC Q 20 V 24.10 Build 122). The experiments were performed in nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of 20 °C min⁻¹ in the temperature range 0 to 500 °C and Thermal Gravimetric Analysis, TGA (Instrument SDT Q 600 V 20.9 Build 20). The experiments were performed in nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of 20 °C min⁻¹ in the temperature range 0 to 600 °C (Fig. 3). The DSC thermogram confirms the melting point at about 69.59 °C and other properties.

Reaction order :

Oxidation of HDA by DPC in aqueous alkaline medium proceeds slowly in the absence of Mn^{II} which was confirmed from the scan spectrum curves as in

Fig. 2. GC-MS spectrum of caprolactam showed molecular ion peak at *m/z* 113 amu.

the Fig. 4. The almost similar color changes observed in both catalyzed and uncatalyzed reactions indicate that, they progress in the same paths. Rate constants of catalyzed reaction is calculated by the equation, $k_C = k_T - k_U$. Since, the total rate constant (k_T) is the sum of the rate constants of the catalysed (k_C) and uncatalysed (k_U) reactions. Hence, the reaction orders have been determined from the slopes of $\log k_C$ verses $\log [\text{concentration}]$ plots by varying the concentrations of HDA, Mn^{II}, KIO₄ and KOH as mentioned in the Table 1.

Table 1. Effect of variation of [DPC], [HDA], [Mn^{II}], [IO₄⁻] and [OH⁻] on the Mn^{II} catalyzed oxidation of HDA by DPC in aqueous alkaline medium at 28 °C; *I* = 0.1 mol dm⁻³

[DPC]×10 ⁵ (mol dm ⁻³)	[HDA]×10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	[OH ⁻] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Mn ^{II}]×10 ⁶ (mol dm ⁻³)	[IO ₄ ⁻]×10 ⁵ (mol dm ⁻³)	<i>k</i> _T ×10 ² (min ⁻¹)	<i>k</i> _U ×10 ³ (min ⁻¹)	<i>k</i> _C ×10 ² (min ⁻¹)	
							Expt. ^a	Calcd. ^b
0.2	1.0	0.2	1.0	1.0	1.68	4.40	1.24	1.25
0.5	1.0	0.2	1.0	1.0	1.64	4.42	1.20	1.25
1.0	1.0	0.2	1.0	1.0	1.66	4.40	1.22	1.25
1.5	1.0	0.2	1.0	1.0	1.63	4.41	1.19	1.25
2.0	1.0	0.2	1.0	1.0	1.65	4.40	1.21	1.25
1.0	0.2	0.2	1.0	1.0	0.45	1.62	0.29	0.27
1.0	0.5	0.2	1.0	1.0	1.07	2.83	0.79	0.62
1.0	1.0	0.2	1.0	1.0	1.69	4.41	1.25	1.25
1.0	1.5	0.2	1.0	1.0	2.14	5.30	1.61	1.81
1.0	2.0	0.2	1.0	1.0	2.69	6.42	2.05	2.44
1.0	1.0	0.05	1.0	1.0	0.78	3.42	0.44	0.34
1.0	1.0	0.1	1.0	1.0	1.08	3.93	0.69	0.62
1.0	1.0	0.2	1.0	1.0	1.69	4.40	1.25	1.25
1.0	1.0	0.3	1.0	1.0	2.12	4.71	1.65	1.80
1.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	2.61	6.20	1.99	3.01
1.0	1.0	0.2	0.2	1.0	0.89	4.40	0.45	0.46
1.0	1.0	0.2	0.5	1.0	1.16	4.40	0.72	0.79
1.0	1.0	0.2	1.0	1.0	1.69	4.40	1.25	1.25
1.0	1.0	0.2	1.5	1.0	2.31	4.40	1.87	1.84
1.0	1.0	0.2	2.0	1.0	3.34	4.40	2.90	2.80
1.0	1.0	0.2	1.0	0.2	6.69	6.80	6.01	6.31
1.0	1.0	0.2	1.0	0.5	2.65	5.53	2.10	2.20
1.0	1.0	0.2	1.0	1.0	1.69	4.40	1.25	1.25
1.0	1.0	0.2	1.0	1.5	1.27	3.75	0.90	0.87
1.0	1.0	0.2	1.0	2.0	1.00	3.36	0.67	0.69

^aExperimental, ^bCalculated.

Table 2. Infrared spectroscopy data

Compound/Stretching (cm ⁻¹)	Infrared spectroscopy absorption band (cm ⁻¹) for functional group		
	C-N and N-H	C-N	Amide C=O
Normal Nylon 6	1551.45	1045	1645
Cu-Nylon 6	1509.41	1032.27	1618
Shifting to lower frequency	42	13	27

Effect of variation of oxidant concentration :

The concentration of oxidant (DPC) was varied in the range of 2×10⁻⁶ to 2.0×10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³. The pseudo-first order rate constants *k*_U and *k*_C were determined from the log (absorbance) versus time plots. All sets of kinetic runs have given similar nature. The linearity of plots of log [DPC] versus time (*r* ≥ 0.99, *S* ≤ 0.017) for different initial concentration

of DPC indicate the order in [DPC] as unity. This was also confirmed by varying [DPC], which did not show any change in pseudo-first order rate constant (Table 1).

Effect of variation of reductant concentration :

The concentration of reductant (HDA) was varied in the range of 2.0×10⁻⁴ to 2.0×10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ at 28 °C, keeping all other reactant concentrations con-

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Fig. 3. TGA thermogram of caprolactam.

Fig. 4. Scan spectrum curves for the oxidation of hexane-1,6-diamine by diperiodatocuprate(III) in absence and in presence of Mn^{II} catalyst. [DPC] = 1×10^{-5} mol/dm³; [HDA] = 1×10^{-3} mol/dm³; [KOH] = 0.2 mol/dm³; [Mn^{II}] = 1×10^{-6} mol/dm³; $I = 0.1$ mol/dm³; Scanning time interval = 30 s (Total time = 5 min).

stant (Table 1). The k_C values increased with increasing concentrations of HDA indicating less than unit order dependence on [HDA].

Effect of variation of catalyst concentration :

The concentration of catalyst Mn^{II} was varied in the range of 2.0×10^{-7} to 2.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³, at constant concentration of DPC, HDA, KOH, KIO₄ and KNO₃. The order in [Mn^{II}] was found to be unity (Table 1). As the catalyst concentration increases the rate of the reaction also increases.

Effect of variation of alkali and periodate concentration :

The concentration of KOH was varied in the range

of 0.05 to 0.5 mol dm⁻³ at constant concentrations of HDA, DPC and ionic strength of 0.1 mol dm⁻³ at 28 °C. The rate constant increased with increase in [KOH] indicating less than unit order dependence on [alkali]. The effect of [IO₄⁻] was observed by varying the concentration from 2.0×10^{-6} to 2.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ range, keeping all other reactant concentrations constant. It was found that the rate constants decreased with an increase in KIO₄ concentration indicating less than zero order dependence on concentration of KIO₄ (Table 1).

Effect of ionic strength and dielectric constant :

Ionic strength was varied between 0.02 to 0.2 mol dm⁻³ by the addition of KNO₃ at constant [DPC], [HDA], [OH⁻] and [IO₄⁻]. Similarly, dielectric constant of the medium was varied by adding dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) in the range of 5 to 25%. It was found that ionic strength and dielectric constant of the medium have no significant effect on the rate of reaction there by indicating insensitive nature of reaction to ionic strength and dielectric constant of the medium (Fig. 5 and Table 3).

Effect of initially added product :

The externally added product Cu^{II} in the range 1.0×10^{-4} to 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ did not have any significant effect on the rate of reaction.

Fig. 5. Plots of $\log k_C$ vs $l^{1/2}$ and $\log k_C$ vs $1/d$.

$2 + \log k$	$1/d$	$2 + \log k$	\sqrt{l}
0.3980	0.000127	0.478	0.141
0.3990	0.00013	0.576	0.223
0.4020	0.000133	0.500	0.316
0.3150	0.000136	0.511	0.387
0.4125	0.000139	0.480	0.447

Thus, from the above observed results, the experimentally investigated rate equation for the title reaction is written as;

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{HDA}]^{0.82} [\text{OH}^-]^{0.68} [\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{-2}]^{-0.92} \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$$

The experimentally determined order with respect to reductant is verified by plotting graph of rate constants vs [HDA] and $[\text{HDA}]^{0.82}$ as shown in the Fig. 6. The better linearity of the plot for rate constants vs $[\text{HDA}]^{0.82}$ indicate estimated order for reductant is in good agreement with experimental findings.

Similarly order with respect to alkali is verified by plotting graph of rate constants vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ and $[\text{OH}^-]^{0.68}$ as shown in the Fig. 7.

Polymerization study :

The reaction mixture was mixed with acrylonitrile monomer and kept for overnight in a closed flask. On dilution with methanol, no precipitate was formed, indicating the absence of intervention of free radicals in the reaction. This observation also supports the polymerization of non-olefinic monomers.

Fig. 6. Plots of k_C vs $[\text{HDA}] \text{ mol/dm}^3$ and k_C vs $[\text{HDA}]^{0.82} \text{ mol/dm}^3$.

Effect of temperature :

The temperature effect on rate constants for both catalysed and uncatalysed reactions was studied at 28, 35, 40 and 45 °C. The rate constants increased with an increase in temperature for both the reactions, indicating endothermic nature of reaction. The plots of $2 + \log k_C$ and $3 + \log k_U$ versus $1/T$ yield

Fig. 7. Plots of k_C vs $[\text{OH}^-] \text{ mol/dm}^3$ and k_C vs $[\text{OH}^-]^{0.68} \text{ mol/dm}^3$.

Table 4. Activation parameters for Mn^{II} catalyzed oxidation of hexane-1,6-diamine by diperiodatocuprate(III) in aqueous alkaline medium at different temperatures

Temp. (K)	ΔE^\ddagger (kJ/mol)		ΔH^\ddagger (kJ/mol)		ΔS^\ddagger (JK mol ⁻¹)		log A		ΔG^\ddagger (kJ/mol)	
	Uncat.	Cat.	Uncat.	Cat.	Uncat.	Cat.	Uncat.	Cat.	Uncat.	Cat.
301	46.69	17.15	44.19	14.64	83.76	-12.28	6.00	1.07	18.98	18.33
308	97.91	-97.8	95.41	-100.3	-254.82	-394.20	14.63	-18.88	18.71	10.91
331	-94.83	-99.7	-97.3	-102.2	-385.50	-400.67	6.243	-17.31	18.70	11.03
318	-96.42	-97.3	-98.9	-99.87	-390.78	-393.02	-2.37	-18.80	18.71	18.43

Uncat. – Uncatalysed, Cat. – Catalysed.

Fig. 8. Plot of log *k* vs 1/*T* for catalyzed and uncatalyzed reactions.

straight line (Fig. 8) and the values of activation parameters viz. enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger), entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) and Gibb's free energy (ΔG^\ddagger) are evaluated from the slopes of the plots by using the Eyring equation^{12,13} and are tabulated in Table 4. We have observed that increase in alkali concentration has increased the rate (Table 1). This finding clearly explains the formation of $[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6)(\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6)]^{2-}$ as shown in the following equilibrium;

The retarding effect of periodate on reaction rate suggests the formation of monoperiodatocuprate(III) (MPC) species form $[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6)(\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6)]^{2-}$.

The above stated equilibrium (1) and (2) have been reported by many researchers¹⁴ in aqueous alkaline medium. Thus lower periodate complex, MPC, is considered as a reactive species among all forms of DPC. Less than zero order in periodate is also due to the formation of MPC as given in equilibrium (2). Mn^{II} acts as an efficient catalyst in many of the redox reaction, particularly in alkaline medium. It was found that in alkaline medium Mn^{II} exists as fairly unstable manganese peroxide^{5,15}. The reaction Mn^{II} catalyzed oxidation of HDA by DPC in aqueous alkaline medium has the stoichiometry 1 : 4 (HDA : DPC) with first order dependence on both [DPC] and Mn^{II} and an order of less than unity both on [HDA] and [OH⁻], a negative fractional order dependence on [periodate]. No effect of added product Cu^{II} was observed.

Based on the experimental results, a mechanism is proposed for which all the observed orders in [DPC], [HDA], [OH⁻], [Mn^{II}] and [IO₄⁻]. Less than unit order in HDA presumably results from the formation of a complex, C₁, between the Mn^{II} species and HDA. Complex, C₁ was identified by UV-Vis spectra, Michaelis-Menten plot (Fig. 9), FTIR (Table 5). Spec-

Table 5. Shifting of frequencis shows formation of complex C₁

Compound/Stretching (cm ⁻¹)	C-N	N-H	C-H(sp ³)
HDA	1180	3339	2934, 2856
Complex C ₁	1197	3421	2925, 2852

Fig. 9. Order with respect HDA and OH⁻ ion concentration on the Mn^{II} catalyzed oxidation of hexane-1,6-diamine by diperiodatocuprate(III) in aqueous alkaline medium at 28 °C.

troscopic evidence for the complex formation between manganese(II) and hexane-1,6-diamine was obtained from UV-Vis spectra of hexane-1,6-diamine, manganese(II) separately in presence of alkali and a mixture of both in the same medium. A bathochromic shift of about 2 nm from 316 nm to 318 nm in the spectra of HDA was observed. The Michaelis-Menten plot also proved the complex formation between catalyst and reductant, which explains the less than unit order dependence on [HDA]. Such type of complex between a substrate and a catalyst has been observed in other studies¹⁶. The brownish yellow coloured HDA-Mn^{II} complex generated reacts immediately with two moles of MPC and alkali in a fast step to give the intermediate water soluble colourless crystalline compound of n-(6-aminoethyl)hydroxylamine and Cu^{II} species with the regeneration of catalyst. Thus, generated n-(6-aminoethyl)hydroxylamine forms dark green colored complex (C₂) with Cu^{II} in an another fast step. This Cu^{II} complex (C₂) is comparatively more stable because of its usual square planar structure and identified by UV-Vis spectra a bathochromic shift of about 5 nm from 305 to 310 nm in the spectra was observed, FTIR (Table 6). The complex, C₂, reacts with two moles of MPC and alkali in a slow

Table 6. Shifting of frequencis shows formatin of complex C₂

Compound/Stretching (cm ⁻¹)	C-N	N-H	C-H(sp ³)
n-(6-Aminoethyl)hydroxylamine	1116	3400	2922, 2852
Complex C ₂	1114	3432	2923, 2854

step to form another intermediate caprolactum compound with the liberation of ammonia. The formed caprolactum is the final product of the reaction. At temperature caprolactum generated polymerizes quickly in aqueous solution to form nylon 6^{6,18} which was also identified by FTIR (KBr; cm⁻¹) spectrum (showed amide N-H stretch around 3700–3500, C=O stretch at 1647.77 and (C- N) around 1080–1360 also CH₂ groups at 2928). TGA and DSC confirms the polymerization of caprolactam into nylon 6¹⁹ and other properties.

Lastly, nylon 6 forms stable lawn colored complex, C₃, with Cu^{II} in a fast step as shown in Scheme 1. With the help of Scheme 1 following rate law was derived;

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{DPC}]} &= k_C = k_T - k_U \\ &= \frac{kK_1K_2K_3 [\text{HDA}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]}{[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}] + K_1[\text{OH}^-][\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}] + K_1K_2 [\text{OH}^-] \\ &\quad + K_3[\text{HDA}][\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}] + K_1K_3[\text{HDA}][\text{OH}^-][\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}] \\ &\quad + K_1K_2K_3[\text{HDA}][\text{OH}^-]} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Above rate law explains all the observed kinetic orders of different species. The rate law can be rearranged into the following form which is apposite for verification;

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]}{k_C} &= \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}]}{kK_1K_2K_3[\text{HDA}][\text{OH}^-]} + \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}]}{kK_2K_3[\text{HDA}]} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{kK_3[\text{HDA}]} + \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}]}{kK_1K_2[\text{OH}^-]} + \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}]}{kK_2} + \frac{1}{k} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

According to above equation, the plots of [Mn^{II}]/k_C versus 1/[HDA], [Mn^{II}]/k_C versus 1/[OH⁻] and [Mn^{II}]/k_C versus [H₃IO₆²⁻] were linear as in Fig. 10. From

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Fig. 10. Verification of rate law of Mn^{II} catalyzed oxidation of hexane-1,6-diamine by diperiodatocuprate(III) in aqueous alkaline medium at 301 K.

the intercepts and slopes of such plots, the equilibrium constants K_1 , K_2 , K_3 and k were calculated as $1.003 \times 10^{-5} \pm 0.5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $7.106 \pm 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $6.59 \pm 0.03 \times 10^{-9} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $1.95 \pm 0.04 \times 10^{17} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. The value of K_2 was in good agreement with earlier work¹⁴. These constants were used to calculate the rate constants over different experimental conditions, when compared with the experimental k_C values, they were found to be in reasonable agreement with each other (Table 1), which supports Scheme 1.

Negligible effect of ionic strength and dielectric constant might be due to involvement of neutral substrate in the reaction as shown in the mechanism. Arrhenius activation energies E_a for uncatalyzed and catalyzed reactions are 46.69 and 17.15 kJ/mol respectively at 301 K. This suggests that Mn^{II} has played significant role in reducing energy barrier. Same trend is observed even at higher temperatures employed in the investigation. The moderate ΔG^\ddagger , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger values are favorable for electron transfer reaction. The positive value of ΔS^\ddagger for uncatalyzed reaction at 301 K indicate the formation of less ordered intermediates where as negative value of ΔS^\ddagger for catalyzed reaction suggests that the intermediate complex is more ordered than the reactants¹⁷ but at higher temperature

both paths seems to be more ordered. The observed modest enthalpy of activation and a higher rate constant for the slow step indicate that the oxidation presumably occurs via an inner sphere mechanism. This conclusion is supported by earlier reports¹⁴.

Mechanism :

Scheme 1

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All chemicals used were of analytical grade. Double distilled water was used throughout the work. The solution of HDA (M/s HiMedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd.,

Mumbai, India) was prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of the sample in double distilled water. The copper(III) periodate complex was prepared⁸ and standardized by the standard procedure⁹. All other reagents, namely KOH, KNO₃, CuSO₄, KIO₄ and acrylonitrile were of analR grade. Mn^{II} solution was prepared from manganese sulphate and was standardized by EDTA¹⁰. Potassium hydroxide and potassium nitrate were employed to maintain required alkalinity and ionic strength respectively. Periodate solution was prepared by dissolving required amount of sample in double distilled water. Its concentration was determined iodometrically¹¹ at 1 M sodium phosphate buffer solution. Kinetics measurements were performed on a UV3000⁺ spectrophotometer (Labindia make). All kinetics runs were followed under pseudo-first order conditions with the HDA concentration in excess over that of DPC at 28 ± 0.1 °C. The reaction was initiated by mixing solutions of DPC and HDA containing a definite quantity of KOH, KNO₃ and KIO₄ in a thermostat (Temp Instrument and Equipments (I) Pvt. Ltd. cat no. T190B, Sr. no. 1452) for uncatalyzed reaction and for catalyzed reaction same procedure is followed in presence of definite quantity of Mn^{II}. The total [OH⁻] was calculated considering the KOH in DPC as well as KOH additionally added. The progress of reaction was followed by measuring the absorbance of unreacted DPC in the reaction mixture in 1 cm quartz cell (Optiglass Limited U.K. (Q)) using UV3000⁺ spectrophotometer at its maximum absorbance of 415 nm as a function of time. It was also verified that there is a negligible interference from other species present in the reaction mixture at this wavelength. The Beer's law was verified for DPC at 415 nm and the molar absorbance coefficient, ϵ , was found to be 6250 ± 25 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at this wavelength. The reaction was carried for 10 min to ensure more than 80% completion. The first order rate constants, k_{obs} , were calculated from slopes of log [DPC] versus time plots for both catalyzed and uncatalyzed reactions. The rate constants were reproducible to within ± 4% further standard deviation and

regression coefficient for all the plots were performed using Microsoft Excel program.

Conclusions

Monoperiodatocuprate(III) is considered to be the active species of the Cu^{III} in aqueous alkaline medium for the title reaction. The activation parameters evaluated for the catalyzed and uncatalyzed reactions explain the catalytic effect of Mn^{II} on the reaction. The Mn^{II} catalyst alters the reaction path by lowering the energy of activation. The catalyzed path is more ordered than the uncatalyzed path. The kinetic data of title reaction supports new approach for the mechanism via three different intermediate complexes.

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